

Adoption and Adaptation of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Organizations: Actions for Efficient and Responsible Use in Interaction with Collaborators

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this work was to determine the actions needed to adopt and adapt Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) for efficient and responsible use in the organization, without affecting the contribution of the collaborator to his/her work activities. A bibliographic review of the scientific literature and information published by consulting companies on the current development of research related to GenAI and its impact on organizations was carried out. Artificial intelligence search tools, academic search engines were used, and criteria for the inclusion and exclusion of publications were established. As a result, necessary actions were identified for the adoption, adaptation, efficient and responsible use, and interaction of GenAI with employees in their work environment. These actions include the adjustment of processes, infrastructure, and resources; capacity-building for integration and a culture of innovation, protocol development, staff training, creation of flexible and supportive working environments, collaboration with regulators, transformation of work; and alignment of staff management practices. It was concluded that GenAI is having a major impact on organizations by automating processes and increasing productivity and efficiency. It is essential to address actions in three categories: staff training, fostering a culture of innovation, ethics, and accountability in the use of this technology, and its efficient adoption and adaptation without affecting the contribution of employees. This research helps to identify the elements needed to deepen research development and define, in real contexts, the effectiveness of the adoption and efficient adaptation of GenAI in internal processes and interaction with collaborators, with the aim of promoting best practices that generate value through its use.

KEYWORDS: Generative artificial intelligence, technological adoption, organizational adaptation, labor efficiency, human-machine collaboration.

INTRODUCTION

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) is a type of artificial intelligence with the ability to generate content based on various instructions. As Pavlik [1] refers, a machine learning model is used that is trained with a large set of data that can subsequently generate information like the one it was prepared with.

GenAI impacts decision-making and knowledge management at different hierarchical levels, from the strategic situations of the organization to the interaction of administrative and business processes with the stakeholders with whom they are in constant relationship [2]. Implementation of GenAI contributes to increased productivity, task automation, and communication [3], which enables improved people's interaction experiences [4], reduced costs, and being a tool in economic efficiency [1].

In this way, it encourages employees of an organization to develop consistent technical knowledge and skills to work in a changing environment thanks to the implementation of this technology in their work activities [5], which contributes to becoming the human talent specialized in adopting GenAI [6].

Faced with this technological transformation and the growing increase in its use, organizations have identified a threat that could arise from the misuse of this artificial intelligence, so it is imperative to regulate and legislate its use [7] to adopt and adapt the efficient use of this technology in the organizational field. They have also identified that GenAI may incur errors because of the generation of misguided content, which has contributed to the claim that it is not stable [8], thus contemplating the concern that the results generated lead to wrong or undesirable practices [9], or even to diminishing human autonomy and creativity.

Based on this latter situation, it has been identified that GenAI tools automate various activities, such as data analysis and report generation, and generate content that could potentially reduce human contributions and participation [10]. As a result, the question

arises: What actions will be needed to adopt and adapt GenAI for efficient and responsible use in the organization without affecting the contribution of the collaborator in his/her work activities?

The objective of this research is to determine the actions needed to adopt and adapt GenAI for efficient and responsible use in the organization without impacting the collaborator's work contributions.

METHOD

For this purpose, a bibliographic review was carried out based on the exploration of the scientific literature and information published by consulting companies, where their contributions refer to the current development of research related to the object of study of this work. This first documentary research approach was considered to identify the theoretical foundations of a topic that is relatively new in the field of management and organizational study [10].

During the review process, GenAI search tools such as Semantic Scholar, Scite and Elicit were used to access various databases and scientific publications. Search engines such as Google Scholar, Scielo and Redalyc were also used. In addition, the documentary review was supplemented by information from consulting companies such as McKinsey and EY, which have carried out relevant research in the field of GenAI.

The bibliographic inclusion and exclusion criteria were established to cover publications from 2022 to 2024 that addressed, whether empirically or documentarily, management-related topics in organizations. In particular, issues related to GenAI, such as: 1) adoption, 2) adaptation, 3) effective and responsible use, and 4) interaction with the human being (contributor) in their working environment, were considered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Adoption of GenAI

From the opening and creation of GenAI tools, it soon became one of the technologies with rapid adoption and public awareness [11]. This is because the personal willingness to adopt GenAI tools, as well as the support provided by an organization for their implementation, have been identified as factors that positively influence the perception of technology and self-effectiveness in the adoption process for work activities [12].

Organizations must adapt to the rapidly evolving field of GenAI, which has the potential to revolutionize many industries and aspects of our lives [13]. Therefore, it is considered that the emergence of GenAI is a paradigm shift [14] that democratizes access to information and the creation of content, facilitating the development, organization, and dissemination of knowledge by enabling faster data processing and content generation, leading to enhanced knowledge sharing and collaboration [2].

According to studies conducted at McKinsey [15], this technology is widely accessible and ubiquitous, favoring its adoption in various industries as it has the ability to automate up to 70% of business activities, which in turn is projected to increase economic benefits, business competitiveness, and the value of the global economy.

In that sense, the mass automation capability offered by GenAI suggests that it can radically transform the execution of business tasks, increasing efficiency, improving decision-making [16] and releasing resources for more strategic activities [1].

On the other hand, the adoption of its technology in organizations implies consideration of the social, institutional impacts and its governance [17], prioritizing specific needs for the development and effective implementation of its functions. Thus, the incorporation of GenAI tools helps to refine the strategic experiences of an organization and can provide a route for decision-making, as well as contributing to innovation [18].

However, GenAI tools raise various ethical and social considerations [19]. These concerns include a lack of interpretability, the presence of biases [8], a lack of robustness, degradation [11], reliability [15], as well as the existence of false and misleading content [10].

Therefore, the adoption of this technology faces challenges in the organizational context, because users will be able to generate content quickly and automatically, which will change the way people interact with information [20]. In this regard, it is crucial to train the organization's staff to understand and effectively use GenAI tools [21].

Another challenge facing some organizations is insufficient infrastructure, such as outdated hardware and lack of IT support, which slows down the adoption of GenAI [22]. Therefore, the implementation of this technology becomes a complex process with potential obstacles that must be overcome to ensure success [16]. In that regard, Oldemeyer, Jede, and Teuteberg [23] recommend that both

service providers and the government provide support to adapt their resources and provide assistance that meets the specific needs of each organization.

B. Adaptation to GenAI

Faced with the challenges posed by the adoption of GenAI technology in organizations, it is essential that they focus their efforts on developing integration and adaptation capabilities to meet the requirements required for the effective use of such technological tools in order to maximize their benefits and take advantage of the growth opportunities they offer in the ever-changing business context.

Therefore, organizations that choose to implement GenAI technology will have to make adjustments in their internal processes, which involve an investment of time, human resources, and creativity [24]. To maximize the added value these technological tools offer, it is crucial that they adopt a culture of innovation [15].

In a study conducted by Chen [25], it was revealed that the culture of innovation facilitates innovation processes in organizations, as it helps to establish relevant management policies that are adapted to innovative practices in the workplace. In this sense, the culture of innovation is perceived as a key driving force for innovation within the organization [26].

A culture of innovation not only enables sharing the strategic vision of the organization, but also encourages the development of behaviours and attitudes aligned with resource and technology investment practices to generate value [27]. This type of culture is distinguished by promoting teamwork, continuous improvement, and creativity [28], as well as practices that encourage experimentation, adaptability, and willingness to change [15]. In addition, it promotes agility in processes and automation of work [29], which become essential parameters for maximizing the potential of GenAI and adapting to new forms of work.

In this sense, adapting organizations to the use of GenAI implies leveraging the creative and automated capabilities of this technology to improve their operations, offer innovative products and services, and remain competitive in an ever-changing business environment [30].

So, the implementation of this technology in organizations involves a learning process during the preparation and adaptation of the organizational culture. In order to ensure the effectiveness of this process, it is crucial to establish a system of protocols that regulate the use and efficacy of content [31]. In addition, it is essential to involve all staff in the gradual integration of these tools into their work activities and in the adaptation to new roles, responsibilities, and processes.

Therefore, they need to be trained with new skills and competences, such as data analysis and machine learning techniques, so that they can interact and generate value through the use of this technology [14]. In addition to investing in training and development programs, flexibility in the workplace and the creation of a supportive work environment [32] are needed to enable staff to take advantage of the productive efficiency resulting from the use of GenAI and workplace well-being [33].

Based on the above, it is observed that the implementation of GenAI should cover the entire organization, requiring effective strategies involving both senior management and operational employees. The strategic value generated lies in the learning capabilities that are developed in the functional operation of the entire organizational structure [34].

Eskandar and collaborators [35] stress the importance of the organization operating in a decentralized manner and incorporating self-organization as a key factor in strengthening learning and adapting to the use of GenAI. As a result, ethical principles can be established to maintain the effectiveness of interaction and improve the efficiency of collaboration with this technology [36].

C. Effective and responsible use of GenAI

Given the presence of biases, hallucinations, and a lack of robustness in the content generated by GenAI technology, organizations have to play a proactive role in their commercial applications and work with regulators to ensure a safe and competitive future with this machinery [15].

As organizations adapt and implement it, they will therefore be able to understand its potential and harness its value to facilitate their decision-making processes. The effective use of GenAI tools contributes to the automation of tasks that previously required a high consumption of time and resources. The benefits of integrating this technology into organizations are reflected in the ability to maintain a competitive level in a dynamic environment, as they contribute to the optimization and improvement of operations, as well as facilitating the creation of creative and personalized products and services [30].

It is highlighted that, thanks to the effective use of this technology, continuous improvement processes enhance the profits of the organization, as well as the proactivity of staff for decision-making and problem-solving [37]. Also, the effectiveness of their use requires the organization to transform the nature of jobs and orient new skills to create a modern workplace [38].

Wulf and Meierhofer [39] determined that effective use of this technology brings benefits to customers, such as the creation of new sales and communication channels that translate into higher revenues. There is also automation of processes and better use of information resources, which contributes to increased organizational efficiency.

Thus, the effectiveness of artificial intelligence tools contributes to a number of significant changes, mainly derived from the automation of interactions, which directly impact customer service [2]. Among these changes are greater speed in processes, efficient problem resolution, 24-hour service availability, and personalization in care. These consequences translate into increased levels of satisfaction for both organizations and customers.

Also, the adoption of artificial intelligence has had a significant impact in the field of media communication, enabling the transformation of data into narrative texts and news, reducing and even eliminating the need for human intervention for the generation of informative content [40]. With regard to human resource management, GenAI tools can streamline planning, job description, recruitment, and training processes [41].

Finally, it is crucial to consider that the effective implementation of GenAI must cover both technological and human aspects. In this regard, staff management practices must be aligned to facilitate the productive use of this technology for the development of both the organization and its employees [42] and to guide its adoption and adaptation in the workplace through information and training programs that reduce resistance to change, the perception of labor threats, and the lack of understanding of its functioning [38].

D. Interaction of GenAI with human beings in their working environment

Task automation has an impact on job design and has the potential to significantly influence people's performance. Gregory and Gupta [43] conclude that GenAI offers a significant opportunity for human-robot interaction. Among these benefits are: interaction and reliability, collaboration and cooperation.

Therefore, organizations must learn how to improve interaction with GenAI through adaptive strategies, as well as examine the challenges and opportunities associated with this integration [37].

But there is also the prospect that organizations need to ensure a healthy and efficient relationship between humans and robots by promoting a harmonious collaboration between technology and staff [32]. It is important for humans and machines to establish a seamless working connection by defining clear roles and responsibilities and implementing effective communication channels to maximize results [41]. Recent studies [44] point out that organizations that complement the efforts and skills of their employees with GenAI technologies contribute to increasing their capacity and productivity, generating value for the company.

The benefits of GenAI technology are reflected in supporting job autonomy by automating repetitive tasks, increasing the complexity of tasks to challenge employees, enabling specialization in niche areas, and enhancing information processing for faster decision-making [38]. This can lead to the development of improved innovative behaviors in the employees of a company, such as creative problem-solving and proactive idea generation, which translates into significant improvements in efficiency, productivity, and the quality of the work done [45].

In this way, the implementation of this technology has a significant impact on the skills of staff by facilitating the automation of tasks, troubleshooting [33], improving efficiency and production, guaranteeing job safety, promoting the development of new skills, such as data analysis and algorithm design [46], fostering innovation in their work through creative problem-solving, and enhancing job satisfaction by reducing repetitive tasks and enabling focus on strategic initiatives [38].

In a study by consulting firm EY [47] identified that employees in organizations have increased the delegation of routine tasks to GenAI systems, allowing more time to invest in more strategic and complex roles, which has improved human skills such as strategic thinking, empathy, and creativity.

According to Brynjolfsson, Li, and Raymond [48], the collaborative use of GenAI tools can improve working practices, encourage the development of skills and knowledge in staff with lower levels of performance, and increase their effectiveness in their work, allowing them to engage in more complex tasks. Therefore, the use of this technology must be oriented towards facilitating the rapid, skilled, and effective performance of each person by providing real-time insights, task automation, and personalized recommendations to optimize workflow and decision-making [49].

However, these benefits are achieved as long as there is intentional and functional collaboration between people and technology [38]. Therefore, adaptation to GenAI involves taking advantage of the self-learning capabilities that are being developed in the interaction and collaboration between this technology and humans [34]. This process enriches organizational learning, guiding the organization towards gaining a competitive advantage.

On the basis of the results obtained in this bibliographic review, factors have been identified to determine the actions necessary for the responsible adoption and adaptation of GenAI in an organizational context. As a summary, the following table presents the relevant aspects that require attention in future research on this subject.

Table 1. Actions to adopt, adapt, and responsibly use GenAI in organizations.

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Required Actions</i>
Adoption	Adjust processes towards automation. Connect the infrastructure and resources for use. Prioritize needs of social and institutional impact. Training staff towards the effective use of this technology.
Adaptation	Develop integration and adaptation capabilities. Adjust internal processes. Building a culture of innovation. Take advantage of the benefits of this technology to improve operations. Establish protocols for content usage and effectiveness. Involve and gradually integrate staff to their use. Training staff with new skills and competences for the effective use of tools. Create flexibility and a supportive working environment. Establish self-organization.
Efficient and responsible use	Play a proactive role in your commercial applications. Collaborate in the ethical and responsible use of this technology. Transform the job. Guidance new skills to create a modern workplace. Align staff management practices with the productive use of this technology. Give usage guidance in order to reduce implementation barriers.
Interrelation with the human being in his/her working environment	Learn to interact healthy and efficiently with this technology. Encourage staff to use GenAI tools to connect with the benefits of this technology. Collaborative use of GenAI tools in working and functional practices. Take advantage of organizational learning.

Innovation in an organization's internal processes requires the effective integration of its resources and capabilities, as well as the implementation of strategies that drive business competitiveness. In this regard, the adoption and adaptation of the use of GenAI as a technological tool to improve the efficiency of interaction activities and processes is fundamental. To achieve this, it is essential to manage knowledge in a flexible, creative, and participatory environment that involves all the employees of the organization.

Hence, robust learning processes, supported by organizational management, are essential to strategically address behavioral and value adaptations for effective interaction with generative technology, overcoming challenges to ensure good practices in transforming work areas. Each collaborator must actively adopt, adapt to, interact with, and responsibly use artificial intelligence as their workplace assistant.

Finally, it is important to stress that these management actions must be implemented immediately [50]. Organizations must act swiftly to enhance both organizational and technological capabilities, foster innovation, and implement GenAI to attain a substantial competitive advantage.

CONCLUSIONS

After carrying out this bibliographic review, it has been found that GenAI is having a great impact on the organizational environment, as it has the ability to automate processes and increase productivity and efficiency in the tasks that are performed daily in a competitive and challenging environment.

Contemporary studies on the rise in the use of GenAI have enabled us to identify various actions necessary to adopt and adapt this technology efficiently and responsibly in the organization. In order for these considerations not to affect the contribution of the employee to their work activities, but rather to enhance their effective performance, it is essential to address these actions in three broad categories: staff training, fostering a culture of innovation, and ethics and accountability in the use of GenAI.

In this way, the objective of this bibliographic study was achieved by helping to identify the elements necessary to deepen its research development and define, in real contexts, its effectiveness in the adoption and efficient adaptation of internal processes and interactions with collaborators, with the aim of promoting best practices that generate value through the use of GenAI.

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